

Relative Type Extra–Ecclesiastic Activities and Their Contribution to the Consolidation of Relations between the Members of a Church

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ABSTRACT: This article is part of a chapter titled “Extra–ecclesiastical strategies based on friendship to improve consolidation,” from a DMin. thesis titled, “Development and application of a friendship program for the consolidation of the members of the Madrid–Calatrava Adventist Church,”—an unpublished manuscript written in Spanish and defended at Andrews University, USA, in July 2016) under the original title, “Desarrollo y aplicación de un programa de amistad para la consolidación de los miembros de la Iglesia Adventista de Madrid–Calatrava.” This article highlights the significant potential of four types of extra–ecclesiastical activities which help strengthening a church. Sports, trips, organized games, and birthday anniversaries were the core activities analyzed, which demonstrated a strong capacity to develop high level inter–personal relationships between the participants. Due to the unlimited structural legitimacy and addressability of these activities in relation to the human being, the author suggests that these activities can be incorporated as a common part of the life of any group which will help its cohesiveness and consolidation.

KEY WORDS: consolidation, games, play, trips, sports, birthday anniversary, strategies, activities, church

A church needs activities through which to express the closeness between its members. They lead to progress in relational ambitus and consolidation. Churches generally have internal

structures and strategies that develop members' assertiveness about the congregational environment and the feeling of belonging. This article proposes four types of extra-ecclesiastical activities: play, sports, trips and birthdays, through which a church can advance towards consolidation. Although the article's conclusions are based on the results of implementing these activities within a church program, they do not have transferability limits. The four activities are instruments of general interest that apply to the consolidation of any group of people, the faculties of playing, traveling, practicing sport and celebrating being essential parts of all individuals, not of the particular contexts.

In pastoral ministry, ecclesiastical and evangelism activity must undoubtedly be accompanied by a pastoral consolidation of members. Consolidation is not only aimed at preserving the results, but edifying the believers within the congregation. Trying to solve this problem only in the ecclesiastic environment proves to be insufficient. To fulfill the desideratum of church consolidation, pastors generally use classical methods: visits, telephone, and deaconry. This type of ministry has the disadvantage that it limits the pastor to the faces that the person prefers to expose him to, without getting to know it in depth. Today, people have high expectations, a dynamic spirit, and are particularly involved in active projects with unpredictable ends. For this reason, pastoral attention must be much more diversified and effective. There are alternative activities that consist in discovering and potentiating the gifts of others. A trip with a group of young people, over four days, offers huge opportunities for knowledge. Relationships that develop on that occasion may be more intense than those generated within two years of activity inside the church

The practice of recreational activities is not the synonym of entertainment. Recreation does not mean experimenting with innocent pleasures in your spare time, feelings of cheap holiness or convenience on devotional tones. True recreation prepares the person's soul to re-create; it includes the body and the spirit.

Ketchell (2005), quoting Moore, argues that in the United States, religious camps have reached an institutional status, because they successfully satisfy two relevant needs: godliness and play.

These two aspects are legitimate in the structure of the human being as fundamental needs. In order to strengthen the church, a pastor must find possibilities to agglutinate them in the activities he proposes.

Here are four types of extra-ecclesiastical activities and the role they play in strengthening a church: games, sports, excursions, and birthdays.

Games

M. J. Hess (2012) highlights the clear link between play and church building. The author cites Rendel's opinion that "some churches die because of terminal seriousness," (Hess 2012, 1) Hess himself sees the churches walking in the "valley of the shadow of death" because "the idea of holiness was often associated with an implacable and sober God." As a solution, Hess considers that, on this subject, there is a need for a paradigm shift in the church.

Joviality is an ingredient that can be applied in all areas of pastoral ministry, including leadership, conflict management, evangelism, committee meetings, or worship. Its potential is limited only by the limits of personal imagination.

Showing the role of joviality does not mean presenting a seminar about humor into the church. The game is not a specific singular activity, an episode or a strategy. It is rather a mix of happy experiences, a road that leads the church to consolidation. A jovial recreation has present and future benefits, maintaining the group united.

Moltmann (1972) considers that North American Protestant churches pay a great tribute to puritan ethics on work. This has generated a false notion of the playing spirit, considering it a waste of time or madness. Instead, the work had come to be considered almost a sacred ritual.

The theme of the game has been studied by philosophers, scholars and used and evaluated by educators or therapists over the centuries. It has been and continues to be an important area of concern and research. Huizinga (2015) wrote at the beginning of

the 1940s that the human being is not defined only as *Homo sapiens* but also as *Homo ludens*. Although he wrote in a historical period that wasn't very generous with the playful spirit (around the Second World War), this author sees the human being as a player. For this historian of philosophy, play is an essential part of every person, regardless of the degree of acceptance of this aspect from the person.

Koppel (2008) invites religious leaders to discover the vitality of faith in live, creative and playful experiences. He considers the game a materialized theology, the key element of pastoral ministry. In his view, the field of play is a suitable metaphor for ministry. As a teacher, he developed a broad theology around this subject.

Hess explores the subject in greater depth and claims that the church must assume a theology of the game. In his thesis (Hess 2012, 57) Hess presents Rahner's theological vision (Rahner 1967) built on Plato's concept: "To play is to return to God." The author adds that the playing time on this earth is the general rehearsal for heavenly dance that will involve the freedom and joy of the heart. For Plato, creating the world was God's last playtime. For Rahner (1967), eternity in the heavens will be the last recreation room. If God is a person who is playing and we are created in His image, it is also inferred that we are players.

On a theological foundation like this, Azevedo (2010) has developed a project to consolidate the church committee. As a conclusion, he noticed that games reduce stress and anxiety, cause people to relate to a much closer relationship and feel more comfortable with each other. People who play together have more easily accepted the different opinions of others.

In spite of the above, constituting a church environment in which people can play and pray together is a challenging objective. There are mentalities for which, what is funny, amusing cannot be holy. It is inconceivable that a holy thing can generate joy and laughter.

Koppel considered that "playing is not easy for adults" (Koppel 2008, 5). The game invitation must receive an acceptance response from different people. But the situation is not easy. Generally, adults like to have control. A game has its rules, its unknowns and attracts a certain degree of risk. Sometimes it puts participants in situations

where they feel incompetent or ridiculous. That is why it is quite difficult for adults to play.

Games have different purposes. Some of them consist of precise exercises that stimulate a greater openness of people in their relationship with others to break down communication barriers. Other games seek to awaken people's sense of solidarity. Others aim for a more effective collaboration that removes indifference or the desire for domination on the part of some. There are also games that lead participants to personal introspection to discover their own abilities, inclinations or limits. At each play, participants can be invited to share ideas, tastes and passions, and join in prayer groups or initiatives.

Playing is not something people simply want, it's something they have to decide. In order to be able to decide to play, a more prominent identification is needed with the happy side of life. In this way, the game can become part of our being.

The Trips

The human being sometimes needs to escape from everyday routine to rest and restore its abilities. This is especially true when the existential context is a modern one, with an excess of urban and technological influences. An idyllic journey facilitates spiritual and relational growth.

Ketchell (2005), in the preface to his doctoral thesis, presents the conclusions of three authors (Abbas, Grafanaki and Karlis) who consider that there is a close connection between excursions and communion with God and others. These authors indicate three transcendent effects that a trip can have. The first is communion with God and the facilitation of spiritual growth. The second is to discover the meaning of life as an opportunity for self-discovery. The third is connecting with the group to get the sense of belonging in the context of this strongly fragmented social life.

Trips usually attract people who enjoy traveling and who are characterized by a recreational ethos. In order to involve less passionate travelers or less economic possibilities and / or

reluctant to long distance travel, different types of excursions can be envisaged: weekend excursions for groups of up to 40 people or one-day others for various groups or for the whole church.

Well-organized, combining planned and improvised activities, trips can increase the relational climate among the participants and can contribute to the development of their friendship.

The Sport

We live in a culture saturated with sports. It has been converted into an universal language and church members are also very connected to it. There are churches that organize sportive activities as a strategy to make themselves known to others.

Rodger (1993) considers that there is a rather strong theological foundation on which to base a department of sports in the church. Wyman (2010) is of the opinion that among the many qualities God possesses, a few belong to the sporting environment: redeeming, relational, creative, liberating and gracious.

Although he particularly studied sport in relation to church growth, Wyman (2010) offers three observations on the role of sport in human relations. The first states that sport builds new relational bridges between the participants. The second looks at sport as a tool for restoring old, damaged relationships. The third argues that sport strengthens existing relationships between people.

The idea of associating sport with the Christian message is not new. On some occasions, the apostle Paul uses images of athletics to communicate the message more clearly to his audience (Galatians 5: 7; 1 Corinthians 9: 24–27; 2 Timothy 4: 7–8). This does not mean that Biblical thinking promotes competitive sport; Paul also uses war images, for example, without making an apology for the war. The spirit of competition is not suited to Christian conduct (see Phil 2: 3). This must not be overlooked when we want to organize sporting activities in the church.

Sports competitions, such as football games, can be designed in a way that is enjoyable. A census and some friendly and conciliatory sanctions change the dynamics of confrontation in a

pleasant environment. Irregular actions can be penalized with cards containing pleasant tasks that the litigants need to do during the following week (e.g. to buy flower bouquets for the instructresses from the church's children school, to offer deaconesses books or other gifts, to buy gifts for children ...)

Within these activities, the composition of the groups must be determined on the spot and must be constantly changed to give each member the opportunity to relate to as many people as possible and to ensure that activities do not degenerate into prolonged competition between different groups.

Anniversary of birthdays

People, by their structure, are created to share with other people their stories, dreams, or anniversaries. Cox (1969) describes the human being as *Homo festivus*. A desirable and pleasant activity for people is to meet for the celebration of the birthday. The anniversary of the birthday surpasses in all emotional intensity all other common holidays. There is no more important date for a person, no stronger memory, such as the birthday. In the questionnaire *Meaning of the Community*, published in the book "Measure of the Religiosity" by Hill and Hood (1999, p. 483), under the item "Members consider themselves to be part of the same family" its mentioned between brackets: '(e.g. visits to sick people, anniversaries of birthdays, etc.)'. Setting the birthday on the same level as visiting the sick is to give it a great spiritual value.

On the occasion of a birthday anniversary, people relate physically, mentally and spiritually in a positive way. These meetings offer moments of joy that far outweigh those inserted into the daily routine. There is an inborn tendency of the human being to regain the joy of living. For the church, it is essential to promote these types of meetings if it wants to strengthen the ties between its members. Remembering the other and congratulating him, helps you survive both as a person and as a religious or cultural entity.

Conclusion

In the pastoral process, churches must seek to include different strategies, structures and extra-church activities to develop interpersonal relationships. The failure to adequately integrate people into community life is not always due to personal problems of relationship but because they do not find the favorable social climate. The opportunity to open up and express themselves in a recreational, playful environment can be a valuable resource for promoting their integration. When consolidation occupies a central place among church concerns, as a result, members strengthen their sense of belonging to it, are more creative in fulfilling their tasks, more readily accept differences and disagreements among themselves, improve their interpersonal relationships and their relationship with God.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Azevedo, D. H. (2010). *Teaching a church board how to play: How learning to play can strengthen a church board* (Order No. 3410236). ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (366588589). <http://search.proquest.com/docview/366588589?accountid=8313>
- Cox, H. (1969). *The feast of fools: A theological essay on festivity and fantasy*. Nueva York: Harper & Row.
- Hess, M. J. (2012). *Holy fun: A path to church consolidation* (Order No. 3508411). ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (1019057307). <http://search.proquest.com/docview/1019057307?accountid=8313>
- Huizinga, J. (2015). *Homo ludens*. Madrid: Alianza Editorial.
- Ketchell, A. K. (2004). *Holy hills: Religion and recreation in Branson, Missouri*. (Order No. 3164443). ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (305171875). Recuperado de <http://search.proquest.com/docview/305171875?accountid=8313>
- Koppel, M. S. (2008). *Open hearted ministry: Play as key to pastoral leadership*. Minneapolis, MN: Fortress Press.
- Moltmann, J. (1972). *The theology of play*. Nueva York: Harper and Row.
- Rahner, H. (1967). *Man at play*. Nueva York: Herder and Herder.
- Rodger, O. (1993). *A theology of sports ministry*. Campbell, CA: Church Sports International.
- Wyman, C. (2010). *The contribution of sports ministry to growth in church membership* (Order No. 3407458). Available on ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (305231979). Recuperado de <http://search.proquest.com/docview/305231979?accountid=8313>